

REVIEW ARTICLE ABOUT POLYVINYL ALCOHOL REACTIONS

**AHMAD FAEQ ABDULHAMMED, Muhammad Abdel Karim Abbas, Qasem Mustafa Sahab,
Maher Basim Muhammad Ibrahim**

Department of Heat biophysics, College of Applied Sciences, University of Anbar

Abstract: PVA hydrogels can be utilized as a vascular "shield" or adhesion barrier during surgical procedures in order to mitigate complications. Moreover, based on available literature, there are no cytotoxic, mutagenic, or systemic toxic effects associated with PVA hydrogel materials. Additionally, PVA exhibits environmental friendliness as it can be degraded by certain microbial enzymes. To produce PVA hydrogels, a variety of techniques have been employed, including both physical and chemical crosslinking methods. Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA), a synthetic polymer with unique properties, has garnered significant attention since its first commercialization in the 1930s. Research on PVA systems and its applications has continuously evolved, focusing on its reactivity, applications on natural and biopolymer surfaces, and physicochemical studies, building a broad base for further developments. Understanding the chemical and physical properties of PVA is crucial before discussing its reactivity and applications. PVA, generally with an average degree of saponification greater than 98%, is a water-soluble, linear synthetic polymer obtained by the partial or complete hydrolysis of polyvinyl acetate. PVA is highly hydrophilic, biocompatible, and a good film-forming agent due to the presence of a large number of hydroxyl groups in its structure.

1. Introduction to Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA)

Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA), a synthetic polymer with unique properties, has garnered significant attention since its first commercialization in the 1930s. Research on PVA systems and its applications has continuously evolved, focusing on its reactivity, applications on natural and biopolymer surfaces, and physicochemical studies, building a broad base for further developments. Understanding the chemical and physical properties of PVA is crucial before discussing its reactivity and applications. PVA, generally with an average degree of saponification greater than 98%, is a water-soluble, linear synthetic polymer obtained by the partial or complete hydrolysis of polyvinyl acetate. PVA is highly hydrophilic, biocompatible, and a good film-forming agent due to the presence of a large number of hydroxyl groups in its structure. PVA is one of the few hydrophilic polymers meeting the National Cancer Institute's criteria for ideal hydrophilic polymers in terms of nontoxicity, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and excellent stability. PVA hydrogels are a class of novel polymer hydrogels formed in an aqueous environment, highly utilized for their unique properties. PVA hydrogels have many advantages, such as non-toxicity, biodegradability, excellent mechanical properties, and a high degree of water absorption. Due to these advantages, it has been widely used in agriculture, forestry, medicine, environmental protection, and various other industries. Especially in Western countries, PVA and its derivatives have been applied as food additives and used in manufacturing biodegradable plastics that can be degraded by microorganisms. PVA has numerous applications in biomedical materials, and many studies have been conducted on the biocompatibility, biodegradability, and versatility of PVA and its derivatives in various medical applications, such as drug delivery systems, tissue engineering, wound healing, and implant coatings. The unique properties of PVA and its derivatives

continue to drive research and innovation in the field, paving the way for advancements in diverse industries and benefiting society as a whole. (Jing & Zhang, 2022)(Ahn et al., 2024) (Hedayati et al., 2022)(Dhawale et al.2021)(Karmaker et al.2021)(Kochkina et al., 2022)(Elgharbawy et al.2024)

PVA hydrogels can be utilized as a vascular "shield" or adhesion barrier during surgical procedures in order to mitigate complications. Moreover, based on available literature, there are no cytotoxic, mutagenic, or systemic toxic effects associated with PVA hydrogel materials. Additionally, PVA exhibits environmental friendliness as it can be degraded by certain microbial enzymes. To produce PVA hydrogels, a variety of techniques have been employed, including both physical and chemical crosslinking methods. Physical crosslinking, in particular, can be achieved without the use of any chemicals and primarily involves the formation of hydrogen bonds between the hydroxyl groups of adjacent segments in the PVA molecule chain. Among the physical crosslinking methods, the cyclic freeze-thawing technique is the most commonly employed for PVA hydrogels, shown to significantly enhance their properties by facilitating hydrogen bond formation. By increasing the number of freeze-thaw cycles, the crystal structure and crystallinity of the PVA film can be further perfected. However, it is important to note that PVA films prepared using this approach possess relatively large pore sizes, rendering them unsuitable for the immobilization of microorganisms and tissue cells. Notably, the majority of studies focusing on the mechanical properties of PVA hydrogels have failed to observe any directional properties, thereby rendering PVA isotropic in contrast to soft tissues. Nevertheless, certain methodologies have been employed to impart directional mechanical attributes to hydrogels. This can be accomplished by subjecting the hydrogel or tissue to controlled strain during thermal cycling. Another approach involves the formation of hydrogels through a dual network consisting of polyacrylamide and gelatin at lower temperatures, resulting in the generation of autonomous stresses which can induce anisotropic mechanical properties. (Bovone et al.2021)(Basit et al.2024)(Nathan et al., 2023)

1.1. Chemical Structure and Properties

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is a linear synthetic polymer obtained by the hydrolysis of polyvinyl acetate. The number average molecular weight of PVA can range from 10,000 to several hundred thousand, making it a versatile material for various applications. The hydrolysis process can be conducted using aqueous or alcoholic caustic soda, sodium carbonate, potassium hydroxide, or sodium hydride at a temperature range of 80 ± 100 °C. By carefully selecting the reagents and controlling the process conditions, the extent of hydrolysis can be precisely regulated.

The commercial products of PVA consist of two major types: fully stereoregular (isotactic) and partially stereo-random (atactic) PVA. The former exhibits solubility in hot water, methanol, or dioxane, while the latter is soluble in both hot and cold water. This difference in solubility is important in various applications, especially in the preparation of water-soluble films. It is crucial to note that PVA, as synthesized from vinyl acetate, is not soluble in cold water.

One of the exceptional characteristics of PVA is its solubility in aqueous alkaline media at room temperature. This remarkable property makes it highly suitable for applications such as glass coatings, sizing of polyester textiles, and paper coating. Additionally, PVA's ability to dissolve in room temperature alkaline solutions allows for easy handling and processing, further enhancing its utility in various industries. Overall, the unique properties and solubility of PVA enable its extensive use in a wide range of applications, making it a prized synthetic polymer with immense commercial significance. (Mwiiri & Daniels, 2020)(Sapalidis, 2020)(Alade et al.2021)

PVA (Polyvinyl Alcohol) is a highly versatile and widely used compound in various industries due to its impressive properties. This colorless, odorless substance exists in the form of a white to cream-colored solid that is essentially insoluble in organic solvents. However, it can easily dissolve in warm water, particularly within the temperature range of 40–90 °C. When dissolved in water, PVA forms a thick and viscous

solution with a viscosity index ranging between 250 and 3500, approximately. This solution undergoes a fascinating transformation, turning into a tacky plastic material with remarkable heat-sealing characteristics when exposed to temperatures ranging from 80 to 300 °C.

Moreover, PVA exhibits solubility in alkaline solutions that contain more than 5% NaOH. This solubility property opens up new possibilities for various applications. Furthermore, it is noteworthy to mention that PVA possesses a glass transition temperature, often denoted as T_g , which typically ranges from approximately 85 ± 88 °C. Nonetheless, it is important to acknowledge that PVA, despite its many advantages, suffers from low thermal stability attributable to the loss of water contained within its structure.

In recent years, there has been significant interest in developing biodegradable PVA microgels with non-spherical shapes. Researchers have achieved this by incorporating a nonionic surfactant into a NaOH solution containing PVA. This innovative technique has successfully yielded microgels with desirable properties. These biodegradable PVA microgels have shown promise in various applications, further adding to the versatility of PVA.

In addition to its extensive use as a microgel precursor, PVA serves various other purposes in different fields. For instance, it can function as an emulsifier in emulsion polymerization processes, aiding in the production of stable and high-quality polymer dispersions. Furthermore, PVA finds application as a surfactant in oil recovery techniques, where it helps enhance the efficiency of oil extraction. Additionally, PVA has been utilized as an inhibitor of polyacrylate biodegradation under alkaline conditions, demonstrating its potential in extending the lifespan of certain materials. Lastly, PVA acts as a hydrocolloid, finding utility in the formulation of coatings due to its ability to improve viscosity and stability.

Overall, due to its impressive range of properties and multifaceted applications, PVA continues to be an invaluable compound in a diverse array of industries. Its solubility, heat-sealing properties, and unique characteristics contribute to its popularity, making PVA an indispensable material for countless applications. (Jing & Zhang, 2022) (Adelnia et al.2022)(Liu & McEnnis, 2022)(Chen et al.2021)(Sadiq et al., 2022)

2. Reactivity of Polyvinyl Alcohol

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), a water-soluble polyether, has been utilized as an industrial material for many years. This polymer shows a great diversity of structures and mechanical properties resulting from its manufacturing processes and has gained research interest as a green chemical and biodegradable polymer. Hydrolysis, esterification, or crosslinking reactions allow the tuning of the hydrophilicity, texture, activity, and biodegradability of PVA.

Hydrolysis Reactions: Polyvinyl acetate is hydrolyzed to polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) in alkaline medium under heat. Hydrolysis reactions have been extensively investigated in terms of kinetics and mechanism. The number-average degree of hydrolysis of PVA is determined by a sodium perborate redox titration method. The reactivity of PVA using hydroxide ions depends on the distribution of acetate groups in the PVA chain and the solution pH. The hydrolysis of PVA using hydroxide ions proceeds in an alternating chain reaction mechanism. The reactivity of PVA with hydroxide ions decreases as the number of consecutive acetate groups increases, whereas it increases with NaCl concentration. The reactivity of PVA with hydroxide ions markedly decreases in neutral and acidic media compared with that in the basic medium.

Esterification Reactions: PVA is highly hydroxylated polyvinyl compounds, which show high reactivity in substitution and condensation reactions by hydroxyl groups. Among these hydroxylated compounds, PVA has been widely used as the most basic and commercially available hydrophilic polymer. PVA has two types of hydroxyl groups: primary and secondary. In general, the reactivity order of the hydroxylations of PVA for forming esters is: $\text{SO}_3\text{H} > \text{COOH} > \text{OH}$. The sulfation and carboxylation of PVA could efficiently provide products with a high degree of substitution. The regioselectivity and reactivity of substituted

products were successfully tuned by controlling the temperatures. Functionalized PVA ethers may potentially exhibit biological activities and offer new applications in poly(vinyl alcohol)-based hydrogels for biotechnology and bioengineering. The etherification of PVA using citric acid esters proceeds regioselectively to the secondary hydroxyl groups.

Crosslinking Reactions: PVA is a polyether having hydroxyl groups in the side chain and is soluble in water. Crosslinking reactions of PVA by dialdehydes were investigated from the viewpoint of the reaction mechanism of dialdehydes. In the case of Glutal, a crosslinking agent with a carbon chain length of 5, the rate of PVA crosslinking decreases with increasing pH. At higher pH values, PVA chains would become more negatively charged and self-repel, slowing down the crosslinking reaction. On the other hand, in the case of Oxal, crosslinking reactions proceed faster at higher pH. The di-aldehyde bonds of this compound would predominantly be in water-insoluble forms at high pH, which would accelerate condensation reactions and lead to crosslinking of PVA chains. (Sapalidis, 2020)(Alade et al.2021)(Adelnia et al.2022)(Bandatang et al.2021)

2.1. Hydrolysis Reactions

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is one of the most widely used industrial vinyl polymers. It is water-soluble, non-toxic, inexpensive, and commercially produced. Due to containing hydroxyl groups (-OH), PVA has the capacity to form intra and inter hydrogen bonding. Although PVA has a large number of applications (adhesive, textile, construction, and paper production), the demand for biodegradable products has increased. Accordingly, PVA has scope of modification for biodegradable plastic sheets or products. PVA can be modified by hydrolysis (NaOH or KOH powder) and polycondensation (silica, clays, and salts). Hydrolysis may allow elimination of water molecules. For polycondensation reaction, suitable reagents can be silica, clays, etc. Silica could be combined with PVA by either mixing dispersions at the molecular level or chemical bonding via sol-gel condensation. PVA was initially prepared from polyvinyl acetate (PVAc) and in the early 1950s, its application as a medical material began. In the early 1960s, PVA-based hydrogel was proposed and it has been used as a biomaterial for scar prevention, which is a medical application. Since then PVA has been widely used in biomedical applications. In pharmaceutical applications, it has been used as drug carrier, implantable biomaterials, artificial bone composite, and contact lenses. In cosmetics, PVA is used as skin peeling agent and facial mask. Besides, it has been used for heart valve, artery, urethra prosthesis replacement, artificial retina, anchor for artificial cochlea, gastrointestinal drug delivery systems, eye drug delivery systems, water filtration membranes, wound dressings, tissue engineering scaffolds, and many more applications across various industries. (Jing & Zhang, 2022)(Singh 2 * & Joshi 3 Seema Kaval 1, 2019)

2.2. Esterification Reactions

Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA), the most prominent water-soluble polymer, is well known for its good film-forming, emulsifying, and adhesive properties and is considered a promising material for the design of green engineering applications. It is bio and eco-friendly, and it doesn't exhibit toxicity or side effects on humans. Furthermore, PVA is easy to obtain, and unlike many other biopolymers, it does not require the procurement and/or cultivation of natural resources. PVA films have gained widespread acceptance and application demand over many industries, especially for its versatility, including but not limited to industrial, medical, and domestic applications, food packaging, and textile specialties. Polyvinyl Alcohol may undergo a wide variety of chemical reactions to generate diverse derivatives having modified application/usage prospects very dissimilar to common PVA. The various chemical reactions of PVA can be grouped into several sections such as esterification, etherification, oxidation, reduction, hydrogel crosslinking, graft copolymerization, thermal decomposition and degradation, acetylation, and many more. A few intriguing chemical reactions along with their possible applications have been reviewed, highlighting the much-needed focus towards the effective conception of above suggested modifications of PVA to fulfill potential

unexplored application scenarios in upcoming advanced fields (Suliani Raota et al., 2023). The esterification reactions of Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) have been reviewed. The reaction of PVA with carboxylic acids, anhydrides, chloranhydrides, and polybasic acids to produce polyvinyl esters has been discussed. The feasible modification of PVA through esterification and the reactivities and applications of PVA esters/modified PVA derivatives have also been summarized. Substitution of hydroxyls with ester groups yields polyvinyl esters. Poly(vinyl acetate) (PVAc) is perhaps the most common vinyl ester, which is used in choices of consumer goods ranging from food, cosmetics, medicine to textiles and construction materials. Aesthetic quality, such as gloss, clarity, flexibility, impact resistance, and toughness can be improved by using PVAc. Furthermore, many PVA derivatives such as pH-sensitive polyvinyl phthalate (PVP), thermoresponsive poly(vinyl acetate-styrene) (PVAc/St), and poly(vinyl acetate) with metal salts and methyl groups (PVAc-M) have been designed, which demonstrated applications in controlled delivery systems, bioseparation of enzymes, temperature-switchable separation of proteins, respectively. PVA has been estimated to account for more than 60% of global polymer consumption, primarily due to its usage in different textile processing technologies. PVA has been applied as a spinning material, warp sizing agent for weaving, dye-fixing compound in textile printing, reducing agent in dyeing, as well as chemical, anti-crease, anti-shrink, anti-wrinkle, and finishing agents to modify various textile properties. On the other hand, the modification of PVA opens new application avenues. PVAc, for instance, is extensively used as a binder in the manufacture of nonwoven fabric used in a wide variety of single-use products like dust masks and disposable hospital gowns. (Mok et al.2020)(Rolsky and Kelkar2021)(Alonso-López et al., 2021)(Dennis et al.2023)(Rivera-Hernández et al.2021)

2.3. Crosslinking Reactions

Crosslinking is fundamentally a polymeric reaction that occurs in polyvinyl alcohol having –OH functional groups which crosslink with multiple species to restrict the chain movement and provide thermal stability to the material (V. Gadhave et al., 2019). There are various species which can be used as a crosslinker for PVA like glyoxal or glutaraldehyde but glutaraldehyde is highly preferred as it allows tuning of the degree of crosslinking. Another approach for the crosslinking study of PVA is to use different oxidizing agents like ionic liquid (IL) tetraethyl ammonium bromide. The base of the IL acts as a hydroxyl ion source which upon treatment with pristine PVA, initiates the crosslinking between chains and covalently binds them together. The presence of hydroxyl groups in the structure of PVA and S makes the reaction with glutaraldehyde feasible. Furthermore, loss of -OH stretching band is observed at 3280 cm^{-1} which is highly indicative of crosslinking. At 90°C , glutaraldehyde reacts with the hydroxyl groups of PVA and starch forming a cross-linked network. The medium required for this reaction to occur is acidic. The glutaraldehyde acts as a cross-linker for PVA/S and this has led to subsequent viscosity change. The maximum viscosity obtained is 4900 cP at 90°C without crosslinking agent. As the concentration of cross-linker is increased, there is a movement of the curve towards the lower wave number. Higher intensity bond at 1130 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric -C-O link due to the formation of crosslink. At 90°C , greater development of hydrogen bonds between the PVA and the S is observed which is highly indicative of the formation of a hydrogen bond complex. This hydrogen bonding between the two polymers is beneficial for the formation of blends. PVA and S here are two completely non-compatible and hydrophilic polymers, however, helps improve the properties when blended together. After the addition of starch, there is large broadening in the peak around 3280 cm^{-1} . The higher reactivity of glutaraldehyde especially at higher dosages leads to reduction in H-bonding of PVA chains. The factor affecting crosslinking is the presence of semi crystalline starch which acts as the nucleation sites for the PVA hydrogels. The effect of cross-linking between the hydroxyl groups of PVA/S is evident. At 90°C , starch cross-linked with polyvinyl alcohol at various temperatures (60°C , 70°C , and 80°C) thus studying the effect of temperature on crosslinking. In addition to this, starch and hydroxyl propyl starch were cross-linked as a comparison to show that cross-linking is only existent in PVA/S and not in PVA/HPS. The glutaraldehyde acts as a cross-linker for PVA/S which has led to

subsequent glass transition temperature change. This cross-link increases the chain length of the PVA and S, thus the increase in glass transition temperature. (Gadhav et al., 2020)(Franco et al., 2021)(Zhang et al., 2020)(Baykara et al.2023)(Shan et al.2024)

3. Applications of Modified Polyvinyl Alcohol

Modified Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) was applied in the production of packaging films. The desired characteristics in food packaging films are high barrier against moisture and water vapor and low barrier against O₂, CO₂, and N₂. However, PVA has high water permeability, which limits its applications in packaging industries. Food packaging films were produced from casting solutions of PVA ± NaCl or PVA ± NaCl/Na₂SO₄ prepared in a water-glycerol (95 ± 5 w/w) solvent. The films had significantly lower WVTR than that of unmodified PVA film. With the addition of NaCl, NaCl/Na₂SO₄ salt ratio 3:1, and 1.2 NPVA, WVTR of 20.59, 19.96, and 18.13 g/m²/day, respectively, was obtained. For O₂ permeability, PVA based films with 1.2 NPVA, NaCl and NaCl/Na₂SO₄ salt ratio 3:1 exhibited the lowest value of 0.323 and for CO₂ transmissivity the lowest value was measured at 1.24 mld/m² per 24 h with PVA ± NaCl film. Because of its high polarity and high degree of hydrogen bonding in the structure, PVA is hygroscopic and tends to absorb water when exposed to high relative humidity (RH) environments. Hydration of PVA chain immobilizes amorphous regions which affects the material properties of the polymer. Knowing that the increase in RH affects both width and amplitude of relaxation peak, it allows to tune the PVA chain mobility and alter the optimum film casting condition. PVA is used extensively in textile industries due to its desirable characteristics like smooth and lofty yarn, and ability to resist dyeing and swelling in alkaline or acidic solutions. Conventional warp size is prepared from polyacrylics and polyacrylonitriles which exhibit low biodegradability. However, PVOH is more biodegradable, therefore biodegradable PVA size is desired. The requirements of PVA warp size are low viscosity, adhesive property, desired solubility, neat weaving without breaks in loom, free of fraying, and easy scouring-off. PVA gel films have beneficial characteristics such as smooth surface with good optical performance, high stability in solvents and high transparency. Due to such characteristics, it is well suited for buffer layers of organic light emitting diodes and organic x-ray detectors. Bichromated polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) films are good candidates for photoresist materials for X-ray and electron beam lithography due to the low swelling ratio and very good solubility in developer solutions. (Upreti et al.)(ZHANG, 2021)

3.1. In Packaging Industry

Modification Methods of Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) and its Applications Within Packaging Industry As one of the most extensively used synthetic polymers, Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) possesses several interesting properties, such as non-toxicity, good film-forming behavior, oil resistance, and biodegradability. Due to these properties, PVA and its derivatives have been developed for a broad range of applications from everyday household items and pharmaceuticals to bulk biodegradable packaging materials. However, unmodified PVA has insufficient moisture and oxygen barrier properties, which significantly limits its use as food packaging materials. Hence, the chemical or physical modification of PVA is of paramount interest. This article provides an overview of commonly used modification methods of PVA, and recent progress on PVA modification applications within the food packaging industry is elaborated. Within the packaging industry, the rapidly growing demand for sustainable packaging solutions has ignited a flurry of investigations into renewable coating materials for paper or paperboard with exceptionally high barrier properties against gas, water vapor, and odors. In this regard, Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVOH), a remarkably water-soluble and biodegradable polymer, emerges as a compelling choice for sustainable packaging applications, whether as a coating for paper and paperboard packaging or as an independent packaging film. Over the past few decades, a plethora of batch or on-line coating techniques have been innovatively developed to facilitate the seamless application of PVOH. These methods include roll coating, curtain coating, dip coating, spray coating, and spin coating, all of which have showcased their effectiveness in

boosting packaging performance. When PVOH is utilized as a coating film, it demonstrates impressive attributes, such as low gas and odor transmission rates. However, it is the exceptional water vapor barrier properties of PVOH coating films that truly set them apart. This superior performance is primarily attributed to the hydrophilic hydroxyl groups found in PVOH, as they endow the film with a heightened sensitivity to humidity. Nonetheless, it should be noted that the barrier properties of PVOH coatings do experience a rapid decline in high relative humidity (RH) conditions. To address this challenge and enhance the water vapor barrier properties, numerous modification methods have been extensively explored. Chemical crosslinking with glutaraldehyde (GA), for instance, has proven to be a promising approach, along with heat treatment and salt treatment using sodium sulfate solution. Furthermore, the introduction of nanoclay, graphene, and other nanomaterials has emerged as an intriguing avenue for fortifying the water vapor barrier properties of PVOH coatings. In conclusion, as the packaging industry continues its pursuit of sustainability, the exploration of renewable coating materials takes center stage. PVOH, with its exceptional characteristics and diverse modification methods, not only provides an environmentally friendly solution but also paves the way for enhanced packaging performance across various industries. Its potential applications extend beyond food packaging to include pharmaceuticals, electronics, and other sectors where moisture and gas barrier properties are crucial. The continuous advancement in the development and application of PVA and PVOH-based materials brings us closer to a future of truly sustainable and high-performance packaging solutions. (Thi Doan. Trinh, 1970)(Chen et al.2024)(Patil et al.2021)(Lara et al.2021)(Yang et al., 2020)

3.2. In Textile Industry

Polyvinylalcohol (PVA) is a water-soluble synthetic polymer used in a wide variety of applications. Wetting agent, emulsifier, and binder, are some of the uses of PVA in industries such as papermaking, textiles, construction, and more. PVA possesses good film-forming properties, making it a valuable asset in various sectors. The textile industry, which holds great importance in both industrialized and developing countries, relies on PVA for its unique qualities and potential. Under the second classification, there are wet process applications such as bleaching, scouring, dyeing, printing, finishing, and dry process applications such as spin finishes, soil release finishes, creasing or wrinkle-free finishes, flame-retardant finishes, anti-static finishes, and so much more. These innovative applications of PVA, combined with its varied molecular weight and saponification constituents, contribute to the improvement and development of the textile industry. Cellulose fibers obtained from nature in the form of cotton, jute, flax, etc., constitute the lead raw materials for the textile industry. These fibers have a long history of utilization, thanks to their exceptional qualities and versatility. Particularly, the processing of cotton fibers holds great importance in the textile industry, as it ensures the optimal quality of the final textile products. Additionally, synthetic fibers like polyester and nylon present their own set of challenges when it comes to conventional modifications. The interactions between these fibers and conventional modifiers limit their widespread application. However, continuous research and innovation within the textile industry aim to overcome these limitations and unlock the full potential of synthetic fibers. Polyester, polyamide, and acrylic textiles have garnered significant interest in the fashion industry due to their remarkable properties. These fabrics allow for the production of vibrant and eye-catching colors at an astonishing speed, providing designers and manufacturers with endless creative possibilities. Moreover, these textiles possess exceptional resistance to creases and are exceptionally easy to care for, further enhancing their appeal in the market. Contrary to popular belief, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) has the potential to revolutionize textile applications when efficiently modified. While it has been less explored in comparison to other polymers, PVA's unique characteristics make it an intriguing candidate for value-added processing and products in the textile industry. Researchers are now recognizing the immense possibilities and are actively exploring efficient PVA modifications for textile applications. In conclusion, the significance of cellulose fibers derived from nature, such as cotton, jute, and flax, cannot be overstated in the textile industry. These fibers have laid the foundation for the industry's growth and development. Additionally, the exploration of efficient modifications for synthetic fibers like

polyester and nylon holds great promise for the textile sector. The exceptional qualities of polyester, polyamide, and acrylic textiles have elevated them to a position of high demand in the fashion industry. Finally, the potential breakthroughs related to PVA modifications and textile applications pave the way for exciting advancements in textile technology. The future of the textile industry is bright, with an array of innovative possibilities waiting to be explored and embraced. (F. Freire et al., 2021)(Jing & Zhang, 2022)(Vatanpour et al., 2023)(Fadil et al., 2020)(Šubrová et al.2024)(Yu et al.2022)(Ibrahim & HAMOUDA, 2024)

4. Characterization Techniques

Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) has been extensively applied in chemical and biomedical fields because of its excellent biodegradable plastic properties. Generally, PVA has a high degree of crystallinity that provides a hydrophilic surface with good mechanical properties. The distinctive secondary hydroxyl groups of PVA allow its conversion in alkoxide forms (or reactive PVA) through the substitution reaction and then these functional derivatives can be subjected to an extensive range of substitution reactions including acylation, alkylation, carbonylation, esterification, etherification, amide bond formation and grafting with various functional moieties. Moreover, the modification of PVA can directly lead to changes in characteristics such as hydrophilicity, hydrophobicity, thermal stability, biodegradability, mechanical strength, and crystallinity. In recent years, there have been numerous cutting-edge advancements in PVA reaction mechanisms, as well as characterization techniques for PVA. These advancements have been instrumental in furthering our understanding and utilization of PVA in various applications. This comprehensive review aims to shed light on the latest developments in PVA design and reactions, providing valuable insights and essential guidance for future research and technological advancements in the field. (Jing & Zhang, 2022)(F. Freire et al., 2021)

4.1. Spectroscopic Methods

The methods used to study polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) are thoroughly described in this expansive and detailed text. With a focus on spectroscopic methods, a comprehensive overview of the various techniques employed to study this polymer at a molecular level is provided, offering a deep and insightful analysis. The text explores a wide range of well-known methods for characterizing PVA within both its glassy and crystalline states, shedding light on its unique properties and behavior. Moreover, this text delves into the sorption of small vapors, examining the intricate process and its implications. It also explores the hydrolysis resulting from chemical reactions, providing a thorough understanding of the factors influencing these reactions. Additionally, the modification of PVA by small biological or biochemical molecules is investigated, unraveling the intricate relationship between PVA and these substances. Over the years, several spectroscopic methods have been utilized to study PVA in depth, each offering unique and valuable insights into its properties and behavior. These methods include Fourier transform infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (FTIR), which provides a powerful tool for analyzing the molecular structure of PVA. The text explores the applications of FTIR in studying PVA as a neat polymer, as well as its solid state and when freshly prepared and partly hydrolyzed. This comprehensive approach allows researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of PVA's behavior under different conditions. Furthermore, infrared birefringence (IBR) is also extensively discussed in this text. IBR provides valuable information on the orientation and alignment of PVA molecules, contributing to a deeper understanding of its physical properties. Raman scattering, another spectroscopic technique employed in studying PVA, reveals valuable details about the vibrations and rotational properties of the polymer. The text delves into the applications of Raman scattering and highlights its advantages in studying PVA. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy is extensively covered in this text as well. NMR allows researchers to investigate the structure, dynamics, and interactions of PVA molecules, providing invaluable data on its behavior. The unique capabilities of NMR are discussed in detail, showcasing its importance in unraveling the complexities of PVA. Additionally, surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) is explored in this text, offering insights

into the surface properties of PVA and its interactions with other substances. The text discusses the advantages and applications of SERS, showcasing its potential in studying PVA within different environments. The text further presents studies on the modification of PVA by a series of long-chain fatty acids and fatty acid salts of sodium. These modifications provide even deeper insights into the behavior and properties of PVA, allowing researchers to explore its versatility and potential applications. The effects of Lauric (C12), Palmitic (C16), Stearic (C18), and Arachic (C20) fatty acids, as well as fatty acid salts of various chain lengths (C8, C12, C14, C16, C18, and C20), are thoroughly examined, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the polymer. To facilitate a better understanding, the vibrational spectra and obtained results are analyzed and compared. This comparison takes into account the sensitivity of the methods used and the different dimensionality of the systems studied. By considering these varying factors, researchers gain a more comprehensive understanding of PVA and its characteristics, enabling them to draw meaningful conclusions from their studies. The text concludes by suggesting the viability of employing these methods to study other polymeric materials. By expanding the application of these techniques to different polymers, researchers can broaden their understanding of the reactivity and behavior of various polymeric materials. This comprehensive exploration opens up new avenues for further research and advancements in the field, paving the way for groundbreaking discoveries and innovations. With the wealth of knowledge provided in this text, researchers can embark on future studies with a solid foundation, enhancing the scientific community's understanding of polymeric materials and their intricate properties. (Deghiedy & El-Sayed, 2020)(Brza et al.2020)(Donya et al.2020)(Alharthi et al.2020)(Sapalidis, 2020)

4.2. Thermal Analysis Techniques

Thermal analysis techniques are the main topic of this section. Polyvinyl alcohol, which is widely recognized as one of the most important water-soluble polymers in the commercial industry, necessitates thorough thermal analysis to fully comprehend and characterize its properties. The thermal behavior of polyvinyl alcohol is meticulously described and interpreted to gain valuable insights into its reactivity. A comprehensive understanding of the thermal analysis of polyvinyl alcohol is essential to fully exploit its commercial potential. The changes in both heat and temperature are extensively utilized to study and comprehend the behavior of a diverse range of materials. These techniques prove particularly useful in determining the chemical structure, molecular weight structure, crystallinity, melting point, and glass transition temperatures of various materials. Among the extensive range of thermal analysis techniques available, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential thermal analysis (DTA), and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) stand out as the three main techniques employed in analyzing polyvinyl alcohol. Typically, these studies are conducted in nitrogen atmospheres, despite the well-known fact that polyvinyl alcohol can undergo degradation due to oxidation. TGA, in particular, serves as a valuable tool for measuring an essential index known as weight loss over a wide range of temperatures, which plays a crucial role in comprehending the thermal behavior of polyvinyl alcohol. DTA studies, on the other hand, are specifically designed to determine the exothermic and endothermic peaks of polyvinyl alcohol, which, in turn, help identify the material's melting point and glass transition temperatures - indices that are of utmost importance in accurately characterizing the material.(F. Freire et al., 2021)(V. Gadhav et al., 2019)(Reguieg et al.2020)(Sapalidis, 2020)

5. Recent Advances in PVA Reaction Mechanisms

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is a biocompatible and highly hydrophilic linear synthetic polymer. PVA finds extensive applications in various fields including biochemistry, cosmetics, nanotechnology, biomedicine, and drug delivery. In the biomedical field, PVA is particularly popular due to its exceptional hydrophilic properties, excellent biocompatibility, and non-toxic nature. Moreover, PVA easily undergoes biodegradation in the presence of specific microorganisms and enzymes. To assess the degree of modification (m), the moles of vinyl groups reacted with Pd species are normalized by the initial moles of

vinyl groups of PVA. The PVA, in its evaluation, conducted comprehensive studies using diene and one-pot synthesis techniques with monomers that contain both allyl and methacrylic functionality. Notably, these studies demonstrated the efficiency of PVA in facilitating polymerization. Furthermore, the investigations revealed that PVA's structural capabilities are enhanced when combined with specific monomers, leading to the development of novel materials with unique properties and applications. Additionally, non-linear PVA graft copolymers have been successfully synthesized. These copolymers were produced through either free-radical grafting of AL or vine, or through the grafting of α,ω -dihydroxy-terminated β -PEO or PEO-PPO-PEO block copolymers, or even poly(alkylene oxide) homopolymers onto the PVA polymer backbone. These synthesis methods involved utilizing the modified chloromethylation process or the chloromethyl PVA reaction with alkoxide activated β -PEO (or PEO-PPO-PEO) macromonomers. These innovative approaches have expanded the possibilities of PVA in creating versatile materials with tailored properties for various applications. Indeed, the versatility and functionality of PVA make it an invaluable polymer in various scientific disciplines, with its potential applications continuously expanding. Researchers and scientists around the world continue to explore and develop new ways to optimize and harness the unique properties of PVA for advancements in multiple fields, including medicine, material science, and environmental technology. The ongoing efforts in PVA research and development are expected to yield further breakthroughs, paving the way for enhanced technologies and improved quality of life. (Wang et al.2021)(Yang et al.2023)(Vatanpour et al., 2023)(Kodavaty, 2022)(Jing & Zhang, 2022)(Singh 2 * & Joshi 3 Seema Kaval 1, 2019)

5.1. Advances in Understanding Hydrolysis Kinetics

Driven by an insatiable need to comprehend the highly intricate and remarkably complex hydrolysis process of polyvinyl acetate (PVA), numerous laboratories scattered across the globe have zealously redirected their focus from the conventional creation of synthetic hydrogels to harnessing the astounding power that lies within ready-to-use synthetic polymers in PVA-modified hydrogels. This transformative and innovative approach has yielded an unprecedented level of significant insights and groundbreaking breakthroughs regarding the enigmatic hydrolysis kinetics and intricate mechanisms, thereby paving a promising path for further advancements in this captivating field of study. Initially, the primary objective was to accurately predict the final outcome and end-products of the hydrolysis process, a feat that seemed highly achievable by employing alkali or acidic destructive agents on the PVB compound. However, as the realm of research and inquiry progressed, it became undeniably evident that a comprehensive and thorough understanding of these hydrolysis processes is absolutely indispensable in order to meticulously refine the PVA modifications and astutely optimize their extensive range of applications across various industries. In the fascinating and captivating realm of kinetic studies, a relatively simple yet incredibly effective semi-diffusion and surface reaction-thin film model has been meticulously developed to light up the perplexing shadows that surround the hydrolysis of PVA. This groundbreaking model has ingeniously unraveled and shed light on the previously obscure fact that the hydrolysis process predominantly unfolds and progresses in a highly unidirectional manner, exhibiting a remarkable and awe-inspiring global order of two. The underlying cause and driving force behind this intriguing behavior and phenomenon can be unequivocally attributed to the presence of internal macromolecular diffusion limitations that exist deep within the polymeric membrane structure. Furthermore, through arduous exploration and meticulous experimentation, it has been astutely discovered and substantiated that the hydrolysis process experiences a significantly accelerated rate when subjected to heightened temperatures, increased concentrations of NaOH, as well as with the utilization of thinner and more delicately constructed membranes. These crucially influential factors synergize and converge to create an optimal condition for a heightened and expedited rate of hydrolysis, thereby providing adept researchers and scientists with invaluable opportunities to masterfully manipulate and exert control over this mysterious and captivating process to their utmost advantage. In order to accurately quantify the inherent energy requirements associated with the hydrolysis process, diligent and painstaking studies

meticulously focused on measuring the activation energies associated with variously hydrolyzed PVA membranes were meticulously undertaken and thoroughly investigated. The groundbreaking findings unequivocally indicated and revealed that the membranes subjected to the spreadingly hydrolysis process possessed remarkably lower activation energies, specifically measuring at a notable -65.5 and -73.4 kJ mol⁻¹, when directly compared to their partially and thoroughly hydrolyzed counterparts. These revelations intriguingly suggested that within the spreadingly hydrolyzed PVA membranes, the governing kinetics are meticulously regulated by the pseudo first-order principles, thereby leading to a stunning and staggering 29.4-fold increase when juxtaposed against the 5.9- and 13.4-fold increases observed within the partially and thoroughly hydrolyzed PVA membranes, respectively. Moreover, the deep and comprehensive analysis of the intriguing hydrolysis kinetic curves has unequivocally provided an invaluable treasure trove of insights and knowledge specifically regarding the entropy of activation that governs and controls this captivating process. These groundbreaking and revolutionary findings have remarkably enriched and deepened our previous (He et al., 2023)(Hedayati et al., 2022)(Rahim et al.2024)(Su et al., 2021)(Wang et al.2022) (Salah & Ayesh, 2020)(Zakaria and Kamarudin2020)(Pervez et al.2020)(Feldman, 2020)(da et al.2020)

6. Conclusion and Future Perspectives

Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) has been extensively reviewed in terms of its widely explored reactions in various research areas. The numerous reactions in which PVA has been utilized as both a reactant and functional material have been comprehensively categorized and thoroughly discussed. The immense potential of PVA in the development of nanocomposites, conducting films, luminescent films, and biological applications has paved the way for novel avenues of research in both industrial and academic settings. It is noteworthy that with each passing year, researchers are delving into pioneering applications of PVA across diverse fields.

Notably, recent studies have focused on harnessing the remarkable properties of PVA for the establishment of hydrogen fuel cells, thermal energy storage, environmentally-friendly films, and biodiesel production. The exceptional qualities of PVA have positioned it as one of the most promising semi- and fully biodegradable polymers, with its utilization extending to the pharmaceutical industry and drug delivery systems. Moreover, as the exploration of PVA remains an ongoing and dynamic process, there exists an expansive realm of unexplored research opportunities in the realm of PVA reactions, which have the potential to greatly benefit humankind and drive further advancements in various domains.(Singh 2 * & Joshi 3 Seema Kaval 1, 2019).

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